

Supplementary material: User Feedback in Continuous Software Engineering

Codebook: Initial themes, sub-themes, and the underlying codes

The initial themes were created to summarize the important information per case. The cases (P1-P13) and themes are marked in **bold**, sub-themes are highlighted in *italic*. For the details of the data analysis procedure and examples of the coding process, please, consult the manuscript (section 3.6 – Data analysis).

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
P1	37
Challenges	22
<i>Establishing recurring revenue</i>	5
Did not consider alternative business models	1
Hard to sell the product before the integrations is in place	1
Hard to sell to those who are not used to startups (public sector)	1
No contract for subscription yet	1
One goal is to reach x recurring paying customers	1
<i>Hard to set product goals</i>	2
Hard to set meaningful quantitative goals so one uses milestones instead	1
One goal is to reach x recurring paying customers	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
<i>No usage dashboards because of insufficient number of users</i>	1
<i>Searching for cases (user problems) that the product is able to solve</i>	14
Asking critical questions if someone in the team is developing something useless	1
Big variation between the use situations that can be solved and not	1
Considering to shift from being a deep-tech product to solve particular customer problems	1
Example of a case - a ship turned off its AIS but reported that it was broken	1
Example prioritizing feature - integrating a particular sensor if a user needs insight of this kind	1
Fundamental user needs - then no validation with other customers is needed	1
Får mange henvendelser fra ulike brukere	1
Hard to compare cases with each other	2
Overview of the problems that can be solved or not	2
Processing a complex request takes about 1 week	1
Qualitative insight is more important than quantitative	1
Trying to make the product solve generic problems	1
Developing software as a team	2
Asking critical questions if someone in the team is developing something useless	1
Erasing the code that is not in use	1
Prioritizing features and tasks	7
Backlog in Miro	1
Different tasks for tech and product - features	1
Oppgavene prioriteres basert på en felles magefølelse i teamet	1
Prioritize features based on how big can the market be for such requests	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Prioritize the user problems based on what is possible today	2
Standup 1 hour every day	1
Types of feedback	6
<i>Carrying out demonstrations with users</i>	5
Demonstrations to users can be hard for drawing conclusions	1
Different team members follow up respective users	1
Examine the data output together with the user	1
Two people from the team participate in the interviews with users	1
User insight is registered as a gut feeling	1
<i>Metrics</i>	1
No usage dashboards because of insufficient number of users	1
P2	37
Background information	6
A tool to build psychological health among children	1
Mostly designers in the team	1
No need for software development so far, the focus is on the product itself	1
One-on-one app is to help adults to support children with intense emotions	1
The target audience are parents that have capacity to talk to their children	2
Challenges	21
<i>Establishing a business model</i>	4
Attempting to establish a freemium model by giving a free access to municipalities	2
The goal is to set 30 recurring payments from parents	2

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
<i>Finding a way to communicate with users</i>	12
Recruiting users (design partners) for understanding the user problem	10
Design partners may experience value of talking to the team and hopefully spread information on the product	1
Interviews with design partners are recorded as drawings	1
Recruiting the users through a newsletter	1
The conversion rate is only important to recruit users that would agree to participate in the product development long-term	1
The design partners are recruited via the app, the newsletter and the website	1
The goal is to have 5 conversations with users per week	1
The goal of the conversations with design partners is to see whether the product can trigger their interest	1
The newsletter are used to recruit the design partners	1
Trying to recruit design partners at schools	1
Two interviewers participate in the user interview, and discuss afterwards	1
Setting up a hypothesis that the text in parenthesis speaks to parents, while big letters speak to children	1
Trying to find a way to communicate with the users	1
<i>Quantitative metrics are not equally prioritized as qualitative</i>	5
Considering Sanity as a platform to establish metrics	1
Establishing a dashboard costs more than it brings	2
No single system to retrieve usage data from, no certainty on which metrics are the right ones	1
The conversion rate is only important to recruit users that would agree to participate in the product development long-term	1
Coordination within the team	3
Drawing under the team meetings to understand the solution	2
Prioritizing through the North Star	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Reflections on user insight	3
Both qualitative and quantitative insight is important	1
Using mostly qualitative insight because of the need to understand users	2
Types of user insight	4
Considering Sanity as a platform to establish metrics	1
Prioritizing through the North Star	1
The intention is to measure how many minutes one spends per particular screen in the app	1
Today measure how many people entered the app and how many pages they visited	1
P3	46
Background	11
Both co-founders have a [company] that they share	1
Both team members work with the product only 2 days a week	1
Found a script that allowed to run the code directly in Excel	1
Got help from two designers part time	1
Made the prototype that could run the needed script in Excel but it involved a lot manual work for the users	2
The idea was founded in fall 2020-vinter 2021	1
The pilot user liked the prototype and said that it was interesting	1
The product is an interface for building engineers to calculate pressure per column	1
The team consists of the two founders and one designer who is not so active	1
The users wanted to see a working prototype that can perform calculations	1
Future priorities	7
Next step is to improve the tool 's interface	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
<i>Planning development of a usage dashboard</i>	5
Establishing a dashboard for usage data is the plan for future	1
Establishing the dashboard has not been prioritized	1
Initial steps to develop the dashboard	2
The core functionality had to be prioritized over the dashboard development	1
Wishing to have a form for backlog	1
Reflections on product-development	2
Important to find what the customer needs and not what she wants	1
Most of the user feedback is qualitative	1
Sources of user insight	19
<i>Change log</i>	9
Created a system for overview over the change log	2
No capacity to improve the metric now	1
Planning to measure whether users have the tool open the whole day every day	2
The metric helped finding out that the users used much less time in [the product] than expected because they were only finalizing their calculations	1
The metric was created in collaboration with more experienced product managers	1
The user 's activity data is being used mostly exploratively	2
<i>Live coding with the pilot user</i>	9
Live product development - coded while receiving feedback from the user	1
The live product development sessions lasted between 30 min and 1 hour	1
The live sessions were ongoing since 2021	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
The number of live coding meetings varies depending on the user 's agenda and need	1
Video meetings with the user were easier to organize than face-to-face	1
Went for live product development because the user did not respond via emails	1
Were using the users' machines to run the prototype and understand their perspective	3
<i>Own domain experience</i>	1
Guessed what the users needed based on own experience in the domain	1
Technology behind the product	7
The latest version is an add-on at Microsoft Excel Store	1
The prototype has become a kind of add-on for Excel	1
The technology addresses the files in the cloud and allows to make changes in the script through API	1
The value of the tool is that it is easier to work with several documents at the same time, and that several people can work at the same time	1
There were several different pilot versions of the tool	3
P4	33
Background of the product	5
One team member who does not work at [the company] but is still active	1
Personal experience with training and rehabilitation gave push for the idea	1
The athletes receive 95 percent revenue from the subscriptions	1
The idea was to provide people with knowledge on how they can train on their own	1
The product is based on observations from the previous company that people who want to train at home need better instructions	1
Coordination in the product team	4
The developers are not too excited about the user insight, but they like to receive the updates on the metrics	1
Use mission control to communicate with the developers	2

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Use OKR to prioritize within the product	1
Current product strategy	2
Not chasing the users to be able to safely experiment	1
Shifting focus from retention to acquiring new users	1
Examples of changes made based on the insight	3
Personalization of the influencers' profiles	3
Realized that the athletes are interested in maintaining the influencer position	1
Realized that the athletes were interested in earning money	1
Realized that the colours should reflect the athletes own branding	1
No established dashboard	5
Shortage of user insight is not a problem because one can employ other methods in the beginning	1
Wish to have more insight in usage data	1
Types of insight	14
<i>Contact with the pilot users</i>	9
Close interaction with one athlete	1
Contacted athletes on Instagram to recruit for the platform	3
Easier to handle few users to provide the best service	1
Materials sent by athletes helped understanding mental models of the athletes	1
Prioritized the athletes that are not focused on particular solutions	1
Regular informal conversation with the athletes to understand their needs	1
Send sketches to an athlete to receive feedback	1
<i>Friends and relatives</i>	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Initial idea was explored with the external team member, friends and family, before contacting the potential customers	1
<i>User surveys</i>	4
Questionnaires in case one cancels the subscription	3
Free demo is not sufficiently advanced	2
Used [company's solution] to understand why people cancel the subscription	1
User survey to map their preferences	1
P5	30
Background	12
Acquired access to 1100 potential customers in Germany	1
Close collaboration with 5 or 6 institutions	1
Currently 11 institutions with about 500-1000 patients in each	1
Established collaboration with the biggest journal system in Norway	2
Extending the scope from patient rehabilitation to mental health services	1
Five members in the core team	1
Focusing on a subset of strategically important customers	1
Sometimes daily releases	1
Succeeded in recruiting big customers from Norway	1
The product is now in the scale-phase	1
Weekly touch base with the key customers	1
Data analysis	3
Corroborate the qualitative feedback with the quantitative	1
If patients do not respond to the form for some time, the team can initiate a discussion with the care providers to formulate an action point	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Interpret the usage data during the team standups	1
Maturity stage	1
No significant difference in the types of user insight from phase to another, but the speed increases due to the better insight into the domain	1
Telemetry dashboard	13
Challenge is to choose the key metrics and continuously validate whether these are still valuable	1
Data in the dashboard originates from both internal and external data sources, but not from the journal systems	1
Established the metrics from day 1 and continuously updated them since then	1
Established which data collection mechanisms will be used, in the very beginning	1
If the data shows that some functionality is not in use, it is removed	1
See that not all patients fulfill their rehab program and study why	1
The institutions are interested in specific metrics that the product team is not focused on	1
There is a metric to every functionality	1
Usage data	1
Usage data on how patients interact with the product	1
Use group discussions to update the metrics	1
Use self-developed dashboard instead of an off-the-shelf solution to be able to pull data from different sources	2
User testing	1
User testing with prototypes	1
P6	44
Background - product manager	2
Background as electrical engineer	1
Thinking about the application drags a lot of attention all the time	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Background product	12
A lot of data in the product is available which makes it easy to create new features based on data	1
A separate app reads the ingredients and matches them with the FODMAP index	1
A separate CMS system for the nutrition experts with overview over the most popular products	1
After a while the packing service was outsourced	1
Hard to solve the user problem because one wants the customers to search among the producers' tags	1
In the beginning the product manager had to pack the goods on her own	1
Many products that are sold at the application, are unique, but the delivery price is very high	1
The number of users have grown even without advertisement	1
The platform is based on Kubernetes which is similar for many other ventures at [the company]	1
The product was established during a [name of a corporate event] in 2018	1
The technology is based on React Native and Node JS as back end	1
Trying to establish a sustainable business model	1
Challenges - user insight	8
Insufficient time for user interviews	1
Need to wait for approval from the nutrition experts which is a bottleneck	1
The changes made based on the user interviews, were insignificant compared to the budget that was used	1
The choice of hypothesis is random due to lack of time in the team	1
The features are developed based on informed guess and teste retroactively	2
The main problem is the lack of work hours in the team	1
The search logs are limited because the team currently uses a budget subscription in Mixpanel	1
Future plans	6

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Another idea is to extend the app to be a diagnosis tool	1
Need to establish a user survey integrated in the app to survey users on new features etc	1
One possibility is to scale the product to global market	1
One reason for launching the symptom log is the feedback that was received from users on the new functionality	1
The next planned functionality is symptom log	1
The plan is to introduce the premium version of the app (already done in February)	1
Product team and organizing	3
At some point were working on the product mostly on spare time	1
The product team has one day par week to work on the product	1
The same product team works for the customer project	1
Types of insight	13
CMS shows number of scans of the products that are not in the system	1
<i>Dogfooding</i>	3
Product manager 's mom wanted to have overview over what she scanned, which later became a feature	1
<i>Even logs</i>	4
Event logs also show which lists users create	1
Search logs on keywords	1
The search logs are limited because the team currently uses a budget subscription in Mixpanel	1
Today the event logs are not actively used	1
Launching a beta version of the app to test new features	1
<i>User interviews</i>	2
The changes made based on the user interviews, were insignificant compared to the budget that was used	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
The user interviews were mostly carried out with regard to the online store and not to the whole app	1
<i>User surveys</i>	2
Mini-survey on the Instagram page on which products the users want	2
One reason for launching the symptom log is the feedback that was received from users on the new functionality	1
P7	68
Background - product	17
<i>[The product]' restructuring</i>	13
90 percent of the beta customers liked the new setup	1
Deployed functionality for more and more customers after a while	1
Even though the users were unhappy with the new setup in the beginning, the sales went up which helped convince the stakeholders	1
[The informant] talked to stakeholders in other banks to convince them that the sales will go up	1
It was important to convince the product owner	1
The beta version was first launched to just one bank	1
The customer survey is prompted by the thumb up thumb down icon with a potential for details	1
The feedback sessions lasted for several month to see whether the negative feedback will improve after the users get used to the new setup	1
The my economy function was removed but returned due to numerous complaints about its absence	1
The pilot bank had about 50 thousand users where the beta users were about 10 percent	1
The pilot bank was very positive to the experiment as long as they have insight into the consequences	1
The product owner was not convinced in the beginning	1
The setup became the same both in the app and on the desktop	1
<i>The credit card entry</i>	3
One idea was that Master Card was less threatening, and this turned out to be the case	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
The AB test was about which word should be used for the credit card entry	1
The team took initiative to contact the credit unit to offer the new entry	1
The insight is shared with the banks but the banks rarely come back with the feedback	1
Background - informant	4
About 5-10% is used for the data work but can be more when possible	1
Competence in statistics allowed to estimate confidence intervals and not only the pure difference	1
[the informant] was the one to suggest AB-testing	1
Was working with data in parallel with regular coding tasks	1
Background - product area	5
Being data-driven in a product area	1
More teams became data-driven because [the informant] presented a lot of their insight at the shared meetings	1
Receives requests to help solving data problems	1
Shared demo is an important arena to share the success with data	1
Today many more people work data-driven comparing to how it was before the launch	1
Background - team	11
After launch to the other banks the team was merged with another team and became [team name]	1
After the launch continued to experiment with the overview	1
After the success case the team acquired more trust and autonomy from the banks	1
At first the designers were not so interested in the even logs, but then they realized that it was a good indicator of profitability	1
No one qt the team had expertise with the log tool with all the usage data	1
Other developers were not so interested in data	1
Ran data analysis because he realized that there was freedom in which tasks you choose at work	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
The team had two designers and three developers	1
The team ran many user tests but there was also a need for quantitative insight	1
The team was easy to experiment in because the mandate was to find a better way to present the net banking overview for the users	1
Tried to differentiate himself from the others in the team by working with the data	1
Data analysis	8
<i>Explorative statistical analysis</i>	7
Analyzed the qualitative feedback through a word search	2
Competence in statistics allowed to estimate confidence intervals and not only the pure difference	1
Easy to find something unexpected in the data	1
Found different user pattern among men and women	1
Found that 90% of people did nothing after login to the bank	1
There was a lot of unused data in the even logs	1
Ran data analysis because he realized that there was freedom in which tasks you choose at work	1
Types of insight	23
<i>AB-testing</i>	4
Added an entry to the credit card that was shown to be successful through AB testing	1
[The informant] was the one to suggest AB-testing	1
The AB test was about which word should be used for the credit card entry credit card or MasterCard	1
The first time the AB-test was used in this product, and this was a success story	1
Did not involve many other experts to understand the user needs	1
<i>Dogfooding</i>	3
Dogfooding - one can discover a bug while using the application	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
One can test one 's own code	1
The developers can tag people whom they want to test the functionality, but the tester can do this, as well	1
<i>Event logs</i>	4
A lot of data was in the event logs from before, and some things was possible to add there	1
Easy to find something unexpected in the data	1
There was a lot of unused data in the even logs	1
There was need for a lot of usage data to convince the stakeholders that the new setup is better than the previous one	1
<i>Sales data</i>	4
Estimated the increase in number sold cards or opened accounts	1
Even though the users were unhappy with the new setup in the beginning, the sales went up which helped convince the stakeholders	1
It was easy to show profitability with the usage data on the button popularity	1
Needed data on how many credit cards were issued	1
<i>Systematic user surveys</i>	6
Health metric on the mobile bank in general	1
Ran a customer survey to determine the user preferences of economy categories	1
The customer survey is prompted by the thumb up thumb down icon with a potential for details	3
the my economy function was removed but returned due to numerous complaints about tis absence	1
Written feedback from users	1
After the product was lunched to all other users in the bank, more than 100 000 written messages were collected and analyzed	1
There is another survey of users with additional questions	1
<i>User interviews</i>	1
Ran user interviews to understand how the users want to categorize their economy	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
P8	93
Background - company	2
[Unit name] and [Unit name] are used interchangeably	1
We don't communicate with municipalities, [Unit name] and [Unit name] does that	1
Background - product	17
Advanced and expensive aid tools needs more thorough case analysis	1
Another team is digitizing the application itself, for them municipality caseworkers are the user	1
Authority is given to the municipality worker when the aid tool is cheap or simple (ordering)	1
Case workers want to see number of application cases vs orders, orders can be automized	1
Caseworkers have lots of wants and needs for the new tool	1
I've been a full stack developer at [a company's name] for about 1 year	1
In easy cases, they want to automate the application process	1
New tool has built in decision support for caseworkers	1
New tool replace old one bit by bit	1
Now, we have moved into a DevOps phase after a pilot-phase for 3-4 months	1
The tool is made for caseworkers and municipality worker that provide aid tools, not a wheelchair user	1
The users are caseworkers who decide applications at [the company]	1
We digitize [the service] so we need less caseworkers	1
We don't do anything specific to test our solution, our users are case workers not citizens	1
We leave the legacy system to make something that supports caseworkers and be more compliant	1
We make a tool for caseworkers that gathers all information about applicant from other systems automatic	1
We plan to do this rule specification job soon, service released within 1st of February	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Background - teams	4
Context product team, cross functional, autonomous team	1
Slack and colocation create good coordination between the two teams	1
Two teams, one creates the caseworker tool, one creates the digital application	1
We discover integrations through Slack and contacting the teams directly	1
Bug fixing	2
We make small increments and fix bugs as we go, works fine	1
We probe (measure) i.e. amount of validation errors, like when distributors find blank results lists	1
Challenges	33
At our speed, we gather so much data that we cannot use it all	1
<i>Data sharing</i>	21
Datawarehouse unit contacts us to discuss how we can share data with them	1
Developers make rules that check data in applications to decide if grant	1
Development teams grant access to their data through registering your need in a data catalogue	1
Different data-base solutions suites different kinds of insight, we had to change	1
I don't understand the difference between [data platform] and [datawarehouse]	1
If other teams in [the company] set up an integration to external organizations then we tap into that integration	2
Needs from external entities like politicians and ministries go through the [datawarehouse] unit	1
New software allows us to fulfill requirements decreased by law that was impossible prior	1
Our data is valuable for others in administering [the company], user privacy is a big issue	1
Privacy regulations	7
Horror scenario with a newspaper headline of leaked data, we need help to consider this	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
I want a stamp of approval from a lawyer	1
Privacy regulations for sharing internally was a new issue to us all, have to figure out ourselves	1
We are scared to publish sensitive data without knowing it was sensitive	1
We consider data sensitivity when making metabase-views, set up access control	1
We don't know if it is acceptable to show data that lets caseworkers identify individuals	1
Who is responsible for data not being misused, data providers or consumers, hard to interpret	1
We gain data from others through Kafka streams	1
We use data from other teams in [the company], like account numbers for payments	1
We want them to access the data themselves from Big Query	1
When there is a small number of users (below 5), we don't share data	1
<i>Managers' need for data</i>	11
Managers wants to compare their numbers to others in [the company]	1
Interested in knowing if our solution effects how caseworkers are doing things	1
Managers and caseworkers ask questions that we need to go back in time to answer, have to set up database that way	1
Managers around Norway can log in to metabase through their [the company]-user	1
Managers find process time interesting to control resources, we have to check if that's ok (privacy)	1
Managers follow the same measure over time and more operational data	1
Product owner or managers (external need) often wish to see numbers from data, example with filtering on municipality	1
Want to know how caseworkers collaborate with municipalities	1
We anonymize data from applicants so we can use them to make insight for managers and politicians	1
We use our data to show value, show numbers of applications received on paper vs. digitally	1
We must figure it out what data the managers are allowed to access	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Lawyer as part of the team	2
A lawyer support us in interpreting requirements and privacy issues	1
The rules are quality assured together with lawyer, shared responsibility	1
OKR	1
OKRs and the struggle of finding good measures	1
Process time is difficult to define, which makes it risky to measure	1
Showed demos once a month, that was used as training for departments, and we received revealing questions	1
Types of feedback	30
Feedback comes in a Teams-channel where two super-users from every department is included	1
Followed selected caseworkers early on to understand how they work	1
<i>Metrics</i>	21
Metabase	15
a i.e. journalist cannot access Metabase, they would have to go through someone, like com. department	1
[Name] and [name] is responsible for data in Amplitude and Metabase	1
I trust the numbers in Metabase because we control them ourselves	1
If data show that more and more applications come in paper, we have to do something	1
Measured process time is easily identifiable when low number of case workers	1
Measures are gathered and saved through Amplitude	1
Metabase is an inhouse data visualizer for datasets found on the marketplace	1
Metabase is becoming slower as data is piling up, we might have to change our set-up	1
Metabase runs on Google's Big Query (operational data, not user data)	1
User data through Amplitude (similar to Google Analytics), monitoring activity	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
We create graphs in Metabase that answers questions we have	2
We find it appealing to use metabase to visualize data, but have not yet utilized it	1
We have to assess who can access the visualized data when posting it on Metabase	1
We want to use metabase to share data to other parts of [the company], when the time is right	1
We (developers) set up measures to check new functions, after validation we let them go and make new ones for new features	1
We as developers probe (measure) functions to look for technical errors	1
We measure how many applications come in digitally vs on paper, error reports, and measures for brand new features	1
We want to use data and measures to ensure that we make something useful	1
When developing software fast, we need to test hypotheses fast with numbers (measures)	2
<i>Usability tests</i>	1
Focus on accessibility, got two blind testers employed	1
<i>User tests</i>	6
Caseworkers just glance over orders and confirm them by one click (allowed by law)	1
It is very motivating to meet the users, numbers (measures) never gives the same motivation or understanding	1
Visited a store close by on my way to work, they were really happy with the solution	1
Visited opticians' stores to test our new solution, observed and gathered feedback	1
We got people checking if citizens understand language and forms, not me	1
When we start making the service for citizens, then we have to test more thoroughly	1
P9	75
Background - informant	4
I don't really know what our data scientist do	1
I need to coordinate and discuss with other data product owners, which is easier physically	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
It is not sufficient to only meet other owners in the Owner-meeting, need the informal part too	1
Operating [the platform] and looking for new ways for employers and applicants to meet	1
Background - organization	5
90% of consumers sit close by in the office, organized in the product area [area name]	1
After a decision we drill down to new problems that require data to solve	1
As [the company] changes teams start to question their purpose	1
Some consumers need to ask how they can tap into our streams on Slack or by conversing	1
Some consumers we never talk to, they read our documentation and consume whatever they want	1
Background - product	2
[Another service at the company] uses our API for instance to show vacancies within education disciplines	1
We have lots of APIs, one for externals (vacancies) and lots for internal consumers	1
Challenges	26
Contact with only one user group	1
<i>Data privacy</i>	5
Need to store user-data for very long periods to compare user behaviour from i.e. last year	1
Streaming data on CVs is tricky because of privacy laws	1
Usage-data is worthless because users cannot chose other applications, people will always apply for sickness benefit	1
<i>Making decisions based on data</i>	5
It is challenging to make fundamental choices based on evidence from data (story of making budgets)	1
People making decisions are super biased and have to find evidence	2
We have to start looking at data objectively to stop making useless products	1
We never kill a software initiative in public sector, despite what data tells us	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
<i>Metrics</i>	15
Dynamic nature of metrics	4
Demanding to keep measures alive because code is constantly changing	1
Have to use a developer to maintain the measure which costs 1200 euros per day	1
Keep only few vital metrics on uptime, will look into others when we got time	1
Measure goes down, guy who sat it up quit, new guy need time to fix problem, 6 months with no data, happens all the time	1
Low-hanging fruit	1
User metrics is an easy way out, we can claim to gather user insight	1
Resources and prioritizing	5
Prioritize run-time first, then security, then data products and user metrics	1
Talk to [the data scientist] and [name of a colleague] (what to measure)	1
User-metrics are extremely expensive and not even a part of the product	1
We look at user metrics every 3rd month, should be every day	1
We need to prioritize what is important to us, uptime is more important than user-metrics	1
Understanding the user data	5
Analyzing data and metrics has low urgency, always something more urgent going on	1
Metrics don't reveal how they interpret what we try to communicate to them	1
Metrics don't tell us why users do as they do	1
Operation higher prioritized than analyzing data and discovering user needs	1
Ratings are worthless too because users hold such low expectancy they always give 4-5 stars	1
Data sharing	6
Publish data on Kafka streams	2

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Publish data on vacancies through API and arbeidsplassen.no	1
Teams that make tools for [the company]-counsellor use data from us and a bunch others	1
We merely deliver data that other teams use in their products	1
We produce data that is used by other teams need to do their tasks	1
Types of feedback	29
<i>Error alarms</i>	3
Developers are responsible for setting up the alarms (measurements) themselves	1
We don't care about user metrics anymore, now we use alarms i.e. user meets a blank page	1
We got a board with approx. 40 smilies indicating that our 40 applications are running	1
<i>Metrics</i>	15
Dynamic nature of metrics	4
Demanding to keep measures alive because code is constantly changing	1
Have to use a developer to maintain the measure which costs 1200 euros per day	1
Keep only few vital metrics on uptime, will look into others when we got time	1
Measure goes down, guy who sat it up quit, new guy need time to fix problem, 6 months with no data, happens all the time	1
Low-hanging fruit	1
User metrics is an easy way out, we can claim to gather user insight	1
Resources and prioritizing	5
Prioritize run-time first, then security, then data products and user metrics	1
Talk to [the data scientist] and [another colleague] (what to measure)	1
User-metrics are extremely expensive and not even a part of the product	1
We look at user metrics every 3rd month, should be every day	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
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Operation higher prioritized than analyzing data and discovering user needs	1
Ratings are worthless too because users hold such low expectancy they always give 4-5 stars	1
Number of job matches per week	1
<i>Surveys</i>	3
Used surveys to find what users wanted (employees and applicants) and talked to communications in [the company]	1
<i>User interviews</i>	5
We meet users every 6 months, should be at least weekly, internal affairs more urgent	1
User testing	1
User- generated ratings	1
User data	3
Data on applicants is used by [the company]'s statistics dep and politicians	1
We do (1) gather data on vacancies, (2) data on data on competence applicants, (3) run arbeidsplassen.no	1
We have to migrate all user data to new database, we don't have time for that	1
P10	37
Background - product	6
[the product] is a set of dashboards while [another product] is a more detailed overview	1
[the products] is a project based on [another product]	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
The product uses all data from the pilot user	1
The regulation for emissions are coming soon to back up [the product]	1
The solution also shows data quality per voyage	2
Background - product manager	3
Moved from technical support to [name of a unitd]	1
Program manager for a family of products beyond class	1
User-centered mindset came from the experience with [another product]	1
Challenges - market	2
High time to market because of the narrow opportunity window with the regulations	2
Challenges - user insight	1
Important to balance understanding of one particular customer and keep the big picture of others	1
Team composition and organizing	8
A separate team for [the product]	4
Another team is working in [name of a city]	1
Synchronization meetings between different product managers in the same product family to understand the current results from user interviews	1
The senior developer on the team is the same as on [another product] in the beginning	1
Wishes to reduce the number of stakeholders in the decision-making process on the product	1
The user problem	9
Data quality is a problem	1
Data should be as precise as possible to be able to recommend actions that reduce the emissions marginally	1
[the product] shall be used of ship owners and not by technical managers	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Idea behind the product is to show that the data quality is low	1
Potential customers beyond class are not interested in compliance, so their need is more unknown	1
There is an ongoing project to tag datasets with quality and level of access tags	1
Today the customer is not measuring the emissions with sensors, mostly use alternative methods	1
Today the process of collecting emissions data is very manual	1
Voyage dashboard is thought as a dashboard that gives overview over emissions per voyage and not per year as it is with [another product] today	1
Types of insight	8
<i>User interviews</i>	8
Customer interviews are run by people from advisory who own the solution	1
Have interviewed different roles at the pilot customer company	1
It was important to show the customers their own data	1
One pilot customer in [name of a service in the same company]	1
Product manager thinks the most interesting part of user interviews is interpreting the user data	2
Suspect that customer interest is not very high because they did not have time to test the solution	2
P11	59
Acquiring user data from others	8
Cumbersome process of getting usage data from the data team	1
Easy to get hold of the data from other teams if one knows someone from this team	2
In some cases there one needs to interact with other teams to ask for data	2
Need to be a better connection with the data team	2
Unfamiliar with the data team because of the covid pandemic	1
Following-up the hypotheses	2

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Lack of transparent logging of the validated hypotheses	1
The lack of a continuous documentation of the evaluated hypotheses is not necessarily problematic because next designer should own the product	1
Gut feeling as a way to formulate hypothesis	6
Desire to work more data-based but in many cases it is based on gut feeling	1
Gut feeling was used to test the cancel reservation button	1
Hypotheses can be based on gut feeling	2
Hypothesis about the return trip button appeared based on gut feeling	2
Improving usability of the map feature	12
AB test calculator for statistical significance	1
Asking developers (Kanban card) to create measurement of how many users use change of departure time	1
Based hypothesis on intuition	1
Big changes in the app create the need for validating the hypotheses	1
Creating a kanban card to test hypothesis about the use of the map based on its visibility	2
Developers create the dashboard with the metrics	1
Follow up the hypothesis (kanban card) comparing the data with the baseline	1
Monitoring number of app openings and completed purchase	2
Spread the news in the company in case the hypothesis is was correct	1
The change was needed to improve clickability of the web page	1
Reflections on the hypothesis -based approach	3
Features can be deleted if they are not being used	1
Not all the features can be AB tested, it all depends on the developers	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Not every design required testing because many elements are conventional	1
Sources of user insight	25
<i>Adoptive tests</i>	10
Adoptive test is more time-effective than a lab test	2
Adoptive tests give a good understanding of clearly poor features	1
Description of what should be tested and how (is not shown to users)	2
Discussion after each adaptive test to conclude on possible future task	1
Lab tests may not be optimal due to which people are available during the day time.	1
Testing how users add favorite route, taking notes	1
Using relatives for user testing	2
<i>Lab tests</i>	8
A blind user for testing functions for handicapped	3
Lab tests may not be optimal due to which people are available during the day time.	1
Other teams also saw the recording and found it useful	1
Recording video of participants and their reactions	1
Showing the test video to the team	1
The lab test showed that the initial web page was not intuitive enough	1
Monitoring a Slack channel with typical customer requests	1
Slack channel where people from the organization can provide their improvement suggestions	1
Using quantitative data with overview of customer requests	3
Weekly stream of customer support to see how they work	2
Testing tool	3

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Impossible to measure retention rate	1
Problematic without automatic tool for AB testing	1
Struggle with hypotheses testing because of compliance	1
P12	45
Analysis methods	7
Applied growth modelling	2
Acquiring all the data in the flagship app would have been harder due to the permissions	1
Discuss the usage data with others, including the head of the data team	3
Presented the growth model to the head of the monetization team	1
Was useful to head the head of data nearby, but now he quit the job	1
Use Amplitude for usage data because it is the SDK	2
Background - product manager	5
Spending only short time with the product now, and about two hours per week during the student project	1
Taking a course on fundamentals of product management	1
The top priority of the mother company was to decrease the drop in active users	1
Work on [the product] did not affect performance on the main project	1
Working on [the product] was seen as distraction by the management	1
Background - product	16
Currently 5000 active daily users and 765 000 downloads	1
<i>Originally a student project</i>	4
Decided to run [the product] outside the flagship app to make it easier for the students	1
Gave a very clear step by step instructions to the students to keep them on track	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
The instructions were on using a particular library, Android and how to build the content	1
The product was developed by summer interns	1
The acquisition cost per user is between one cent and three cents	1
The content is international and not only meant for English-speaking countries	1
The growth is a bit slower than expected because of an unexpected monetization issue	1
The growth modelling was well accepted by the parent company	1
The idea was suggested by a data scientist at [the company] who saw increased search of memes among the users	1
The product is growing av getting traction	1
<i>The technology behind the product</i>	2
Updating the content with a third party provider - is the key	1
Use common library for editing images	1
The vision is to create a worldwide platform, not only to focus on the users from the US whom are easy to monetize from	1
Using automatic algorithms to acquire users from the countries where it is cheaper to acquire	1
What is appealing to the user is variety of content that is constantly updated	1
Challenges	1
Unclear how to analyze the usage data	1
Examples of use hypothesis	1
Assumed that the number of users fulfilling the meme generation is low because of bad user experience but found out that it has to do with non-English speaking countries	1
Types of insight	15
<i>AB testing</i>	1
Used AB testing to convince the students that showing the text dialogue immediately after choosing a picture, was not what users preferred	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
<i>Conversion rate from Google Play</i>	3
Easier to get users from the affected regions because people from there want to communicate on what is happening	1
Easier to get users from countries that have conflicts because then other services pull out	1
<i>Dogfooding</i>	3
Dogfooding - used daughter 's behaviour to understand how to change the app	2
Observing the daughter realized that there was an unnecessary step in the text colour selection	1
Dogfooding - user feedback from friends	1
<i>Event logs</i>	2
Examples of event logs	1
Was easy to have access to all the data for growth modelling because had ownership of the product	1
<i>Product-market fit metrics</i>	6
Acquiring all the data in the flagship app would have been harder due to the permissions	1
Income per user	1
Number of visitors of the app	1
Retention rate	1
Using automatic algorithms to acquire users from the countries where it is cheaper to acquire	1
P13	31
Background information	9
A user platform specialist helps to work data-driven	1
About 300 closed deals per year	1
Before [the contractor company] there was another development company	1
Exploring best practices based on experiences of the interior architects with the platform	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
Has been working with the company for 100% the last 5 years	1
One of the architects (sellers) is employed to support other architects on the platform	1
Team consists of 6 board members, two designers and the [contractor]'s consultants	1
Technology is cloud-based but planning to create an application in addition	1
The founder has always wanted to create her own startup based on digital technologies	1
Example of an implemented feature - pictures of the architects' work	9
Architects with good pictures have better conversion rate	3
Likes on social media indicate if users like a picture or not	1
One understands that pictures are important because users refer to them when they contact the architects	1
Pictures are used for advertising the platform (product)	2
Pictures create interest for the users and improve conversion rate	1
Qualitative insight	6
Data on user profiles and their requests	1
Personal relationships with all the architects on the platform facilitate the acquisition of the user insight	1
Rejecting hypothesis that one can close a deal through a chat	2
Through a conversation with a seller found out that buyers preferred to contact the users directly	2
Quantitative metrics	5
Conversion rate and transaction amount	1
Likes on social media indicate if users like a picture or not	1
Number of customer requests	1
Sales per designer	1
Traffic on the web page as a metric	1

Case, initial themes, underlying code	Number of quotations
The solution is based on an off the shelf system from the US	1
User interviews to validate the hypothesis based on the market in the USA	1